

A Comparative Analysis of the Best Practices of South Korea and Philippine Education

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ABSTRACT

The quality of education in a country plays a significant relationship between the government and supports of stakeholders. This research focus on the literature review between Philippine and South Korea educational system. It is not undeniable that both countries have many similarities such as their main purpose of education is to provide educational opportunities to promote responsible and globally competitive individual. As a result of systematic analysis of the two countries, similar variables were taken into consideration for the basis of improvement of one's educational system. Based on the findings, Philippine education is outlying in some aspects of educational system in South Korea. Another remarkable thing in the Philippine educational system is the lack of government spending on education, teachers and student ration, internet services in the school and research and development. The result of the study suggested that Philippine government needs to benchmark some good practices in south Korean educational system in order to elevate and improve our education system as well.

KEYWORDS: Educational System, Educational Performance, Research and Development

INTRODUCTION

Education now a day has become prominent thing as it involves most people to take part in this matter. In addition, it cannot be separated from human's life. Both males and females need to be educated. They have the same right to get education as much as they want because there are no limitations for education. No matter how old a person is, he/she can still take education during the rest of their lives. Hence, there is no such thing as too late to get education. High performing educational system is the only bridge that leads people to their better futures.

Oğuzkan (1974) stated that Education is a system which contributes to personal development and helps individuals to acquire the necessary information, skill and competence to be a member of a society). In this sense, the purpose of an education system is to train individuals who comply with changes resulting from technological improvements and globalization in accordance with the modernization (Gopinathan & Sharpe, 2007).

Moreover, the development of a country can be determined by whether its citizens have good education or not. The better the quality of education that a country has, the fastest it is likely to develop.

Schleicher (2018) noted that Top-performing educational systems set ambitious goals, are clear about what students

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should be able to do, and enable teachers to figure out what they need to teach their students. They have moved on from administrative control and accountability to professional forms of work organization. They encourage their teachers to be innovative, to improve their own performance and that of their colleagues, and to pursue professional development that leads to better practice. In top school systems, the emphasis is not on looking upward within the administration of the school system. Instead it's about looking outward to the next teacher or the next school, creating a culture of collaboration and strong networks of innovation.

Objective of the Study

This research aims to determine the comparison between policy practices and success in Philippine and South Korea educational system. The goal is to understand on what best practices that promotes change and effective educational system in the modern education.

Educational performance of South Korea

South Korea performance in education in the last four years has been masterful in execution. Their results in standardized testing and their student's ability to advance towards college graduation is the model over 200 nations, are chasing to be the best in education.

In NJ MED's 2017, World Top 20 Education Poll that ranks the world's best education systems, South Korea's captured, the number one spot for the fourth consecutive year. Even, with Japan closing the gap by seven points, it looks like South Korea will still be number one in 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, and 2022.

Moreover, by some measures, South Korea—the Republic of Korea—is the most educated country in the world. According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), 70 percent of 24- to 35-year-olds in the nation of 51.5 million people have completed some form of tertiary education—the highest percentage worldwide and more than 20 percentage points above comparable attainment rates in the United States. Korea also has a top-quality school system when measured by student performance in standardized tests: The country consistently ranks among the best-performing countries in the OECD's Program for International Student Assessment (PISA, 2018). According to Yang (2016) South Korea are very motivated and insanely intense schools in their educations they are part of most extreme, arguably, and most successful the country is mostly competitive when the students involved with tests, which it's also included the tests of critical thinking and analysis. The students are having enormous, pressure of their schoolwork the children study year-round, both in-school and with tutors, so they can be better in their academics.

Further, the reality is, in the modern world their kid is going to have to know how to learn, how to work hard and how to persist after failure. The Korean model teaches them not to give up, Some parents drop about 25% of their income on education, tutoring and educational materials for their children's And most parents send their kids to extra private school after their regular school day, of how much the parents want their child to be so successful so it goes without saying that parents and students are highly motivated when it comes to school.

Figure1.

Out of 70 participating countries across the globe south Korea took the 9th spot in the recent PISA world ranking. In South Korea the culture believes in hard work and diligence, there is no excuse for failure in their culture because the culture traditionally celebrates conformity pressure on students which can also have high expectations toward their families members. But in Korea the one of the goal is for the teacher is to lead the class as a community, and for peer relationships to develop with each other, The teacher focuses on developing individual relationships with students, and intervening regularly in peer relationships, The teacher want the students to do well in their school by going to school, and working hard in their academics, South Korea 93% of student

United States almost one quarter of all students over all. 1.2 millions of students individual each year failed in high school or dropped out mostly every year, Korean teachers are very passionate about the student's school work and want them to have a successful life (Yang, 2016).

Figure2.

Even compared to the United states, the South Korean education system is ahead in terms of mathematical, reading and Science.

Educational Performance of the Philippines

The Philippines has made significant progress to improving the condition of education in the country. Despite a great deal of progress the Philippines has made, 42 percent of the country still remains below the poverty line making roughly \$2 a day. UNESCO and USAID are working with the Philippine Government to improve the conditions of education. USAID reports an average 7 percent growth in education and attributes this to the weak government in the region. UNESCO attributes the challenges in education to internal conflict and is working to broker a lasting peace in the region (Cross, 2016).

The research arm of Switzerland-based business school International Institute for Management Development (IMD) recently conducted a survey on the talent competitiveness of 66 countries around the world. While countries like Malaysia and Indonesia managed to move up in the IMD World Competitiveness' World Talent Ranking 2018, several countries in Asia also dropped a few places. The most significant drop, however, was in the Philippines. The Philippines dropped a total of 10 places this year to 55th, earning an overall score of only 42.11 out of 100 points. In 2017, Philippines was placed 45th. In order to understand how the Philippines experienced such a huge drop in ranking, it's important to look at what the study uses for its indicators. The World Talent Ranking looks at three main factors when determining how to rank a country: The investment and development factor, which measures resources used to cultivate homegrown human capital; the appeal factor, which evaluates the extent to which a country attracts and retains foreign and local talent; and the readiness factor, which looks at the quality of skills and competencies of a country's labour force. While a simple example of the investment and development factor would be whether a country is able to provide education to its citizens, the readiness factor seems to indicate that it is also important to look at the quality of the education provided. This, according to the study, is where countries like the Philippines fall short (Khidhir, 2018).

Quality of education

This change is driven by a marked deterioration in every criterion related to the business community’s perceptions on the quality of education, as well as a decline in labour force quality,” the report explained. For the three factors, the Philippines went from 34th to 38th for appeal, and actually climbed from 63rd to 62nd for investment and development. There was, however, a sharp drop for readiness where the country went from 11th to 37th. However, in 2018, The Philippines witnessed a deterioration of its ability to provide the economy with the skills needed, which points to a mismatch between school curriculums and the demands of companies,” (Khidhir, 2018).

Educational Statistics between Philippines and South Korea

Government Spending on Education

Percentage of public funding for education out of country's total GDP.

The data revealed that in terms of government spending on education, South Korea has higher budget compared to the Philippines. Evans (2019) noted that states with strong teacher unions, school districts tended to match increases in state funding, which “led to larger increases in student achievement.” Other work looks at the impact of these financing reforms on high school graduation rates: “Seven years after reform, the highest poverty quartile in a treated state experienced an 11.5 percent to 12.1 percent increase in per-pupil spending, and a 6.8 to 11.5 percentage point increase in graduation rates. This implied that the higher the educational budget in a country would enhance its educational system.

Students and Teacher Ratio

Pupil-teacher ratio. Primary is the number of pupils enrolled in primary school divided by the number of primary school teachers.

Figure4. Pupil Teacher Ratio

Figure5.

Figure 4 and 5 presents the students and teacher ratio in the two countries. Based on the data revealed, it can be noticed that there’s a huge gap. Philippines has a higher pupil and teacher ratio compared to South Korea. This implied that teachers from the Philippines have higher number of students inside the classroom compared to the South Korea. Emma (2013) stated in the results of her study that the smaller the student-teacher ratio, the better the quality of education of both high and low intelligent students.

However, the study suggested that policy makers on education should Endeavour to scale down the number of student per class by employing more high quality teachers. Therefore, the students and teacher ratio has significant relationship between the understanding and academic performance of the students.

Research and Development

Researchers in R&D are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods, or systems and in the management of the projects concerned. Postgraduate PhD students engaged in R&D are included.

Figure6.

Research and development of the two countries has showed that there is a big gap between the two. It can be noticed that South Korea is 70 times more than Philippines in terms of producing research. Essays (2018) expounded that Educational research is important because it is conducted in order to provide trustworthy information regarding educational problems and their solutions. There are many things that need to be considered when looking at what educational research is for example some thought needs to be put into looking at current paradigms, what counts as evidence in educational research, maintaining quality, and the role of peer review in validating new knowledge in educational research. Therefore, research and development is a need to improved one’s educational system.

Schools Connected to the Internet

Schools connected to the Internet are the share of primary and secondary schools in the country that have access to the Internet.

Figure7.

The data presents that most of the schools in South Korea has an access to the internet. While Philippines on the other hand, has a small fraction of accessibility on the internet. This implies that students and educator have little chances of accessing the internet. According to the Asian School (2019) *Internet* plays a very vital role in *education*. It is no doubt that in this modern era everyone prefers Google for their queries, problems or doubts. Popular search engines like Yahoo, Google, etc. are the topmost choice of people as these offer an easy and instant reach to the vast amount of information in just a few seconds. It contains a wealth of knowledge that can be searched at any time. The internet has introduced improvements in technology, communication, and online entertainment. Hence, Philippine needs to work out in putting internet especially in basic education.

Conclusions

Based on the aforementioned findings, it was concluded that the general purpose of education in both countries is to provide globally competitive graduates that promotes responsible citizen. On the other hand, it can be noticed also that Philippine education is far behind in some aspects of

educational system in South Korea. Another remarkable thing in the Philippine educational system is the lack of government spending on education, teachers and student ration, internet services in the school and research and development. The researchers believed that Research is a need in our educational system in order for us to move forward and fixed the problem with positive outlook through research.

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